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An Expansion Too Far? The Contested Space of Environmental Policy Discourses

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Abstract:

Evidence linking urban traffic emissions to human illness and death and as a source of climate change is incontrovertible. In August 2023, the London ultra-low emissions zone (ULEZ) was expanded to include all 32 boroughs, a move that sparked a strong reaction especially from the right-wing media in the UK. The policy rapidly became politicised and cleaved along ideological lines. This paper uses sampled news articles from two politically opposing news media to examine the processes by which policy can become politicised. Using semantic tagging, four themes are analysed to highlight the dynamics by which politicisation is accomplished in the media. This dynamic appears to involve prescribing binary victim and persecutor roles, using emotionally-laden phrasing, invoking unfair violations of law and order by anonymous state machinery, and references to physical and emotional abuses on the victim group which is described as innocent and decent. While the implementation of ULEZ was not itself impeded, meaningful enforcement of existing climate change policies have been, and this is often due to the way in which the matter has become politicised. By highlighting some of these dynamics, it is hoped that these practices might be more easily deconstructed and resisted in the future.

Keywords: ULEZ; low emissions zones; news media; politicisation; ideological framing

Main highlights:

- Traffic emissions are scientifically linked to human disease and death, and drive climate change.
- Policy interventions are necessary to mitigate these effects, although some attract controversy
- Controversy often cleaves along ideological lines becoming politicised, like the London ULEZ scheme

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- Ideology pitches individuals against society, emphasising violations of personal rights and freedom
- The dynamics of ideological politicisation are examined here in the context of the ULEZ scheme
- Deconstructing strategies of politicisation may help mitigate adversarial effects on public policy

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Introduction

Urban traffic emissions are a significant source of greenhouse gas and increasingly linked to human illness and death (Binter et al., 2022; Costello et al., 2009; Foraster et al., 2014; Medrano et al., 2022; Pope et al., 2009). Global urbanisation continues to expand cities and many have implemented measures to reduce traffic emissions. An example is the low emissions zone scheme, which fines owners for using vehicles with tailpipe emissions exceeding specified standards.

In August 2023, the London Mayor implemented the final phase of the Ultra Low Emissions Zone (ULEZ) scheme that included all 32 boroughs with a population of 9 million, and an area of approximately 1,500 km². Only this third phase attracted media interest appearing to have been ideologically motivated and politicised, for example, the commonly used metaphor that the expansion signalled a ‘war’ on motorists. Some media went further and directly and personally vilified the London Mayor. Enforcement cameras were vandalised, with the culprits finding folk hero status among some communities.

We know that language makes things happen. Language structures the discursive spaces of our worlds, shapes our thinking, and gives rise to a normative background of what we take to be reality (Hart, 2014; Langacker, 2013). In language, we coordinate our lives. Consequently, how language is used in the media, already a powerful source of public information about events, causes and outcomes, is an important area for study (Bednarek & Caple, 2017).

This paper examines how the expansion of the London ULEZ was constructed in the UK news media using samples of articles published by two politically opposed UK news papers, the *Guardian* and the *Daily Mail*. The former, a liberal paper, has a history of sympathetic reporting on climate change science. The latter, to the right of the Overton window, shows a publishing history of articles that are either sceptical of, or completely deny climate change science. It also vocally supports plans to roll-back Net Zero ambitions as posed initially by the Conservatives and recently, Reform.

The aim of this study is to briefly highlight a few rhetorical strategies employed in the media to make low emissions zone policy a ‘left-right’ political dispute, identifying ways in which ideology informs and shapes how the media can – and do – politicise events that are in the public interest.

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This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the methods are briefly explicated, Section 3 highlights key findings of the analysis. Section 4 briefly discusses these, and the paper concludes by summarising key dynamics in the mediated politicisation of public policy.

Methods

The LexisNexis UK newspaper database was searched for all occurrences of the terms ‘ulez’ and ‘ultra low emissions zone’ between 2014 and 2024. Results were individually examined and metadata, annotations and notes were recorded. Irrelevant articles in which the search terms were an adjunct or an aside to the main story were excluded. The final sample were converted into plain text files and compiled into *Daily Mail* and *Guardian* specific corpora.

A longitudinal analysis shows that ULEZ received little media attention until 2023 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Media attention to ULEZ expansion over time (Source: Author)

Consequently the analytic window in this study refers only to the July through September 2023 period (see Figure 2), during which there are clear spikes in media activity relative to trend.

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Figure 2. Number of articles published in the Guardian and Daily Mail for 2023 (Source: Author)

The analysis quantifies the corpora, and thereafter, using WMatrix7 (Rayson, 2008), an on-line automated semantic tagger deploying the USAS Semantic Tagset, each corpus is compared against a reference corpus, the British National English 2021 (BNE21). This returns words that, relative to BNE21, are statistically more frequent in the media focal corpus. This is a way of profiling the corpora to understand relative uniqueness.

Finally, four semantic tag-set categories are selected for concordance analysis, which locates key semantically-tagged words within their context of use (see Figure 3). This enables us to identify some of the semantic work carried by key-words.

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Figure 3. Top Level categories of the USAS Semantic Tagset (Source: https://ucrel.lancs.ac.uk/usas/usas_guide.pdf)

A general and abstract terms	B the body and the individual	C arts and crafts	E emotion
F food and farming	G government and public	H architecture, housing and the home	I money and commerce in industry
K entertainment, sports and games	L life and living things	M movement, location, travel and transport	N numbers and measurement
O substances, materials, objects and equipment	P education	Q language and communication	S social actions, states and processes
T Time	W world and environment	X psychological actions, states and processes	Y science and technology
Z names and grammar			

Findings

The corpora of relevant media articles sampled over the three month period (Figure 2) are summarised in Table 1.

The *Daily Mail* corpus comprises 96 articles to the *Guardian*'s 60. While the *Guardian* uses a wider range of words (Types), when divided by the relative number of words (Tokens), the TTR indicates *Daily Mail* articles have higher lexical diversity.

Table 1. Corpus descriptions.

Variable	Daily Mail	Guardian	Description
Number of Files	96	60	Total number of articles sampled
Number of Tokens	39,704	73,359	Total number of words, incl. Repetitions, used
Number of Types	5,479	7,753	Total number of distinct (unique) words used
Text Token Ratio (TTR)	0.14	0.11	Higher score means greater lexical variety
Number of Lemmas	4,862	6,584	Total number of base root word forms

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The Wmatrix7 tool enables lexical comparisons of focal corpora with reference corpora, i.e., BNE21. More frequent words in the focal corpus than in BNE21 are presented in a word-cloud formation, with font size indicating relative frequency. Figure 4 shows the relative matches for the *Daily Mail*.

Figure 4. WMatrix7 tagging output for the *Daily Mail* corpus (Source: Author)

Figure 5 shows the comparison for the *Guardian* corpus with BNE21.

Figure 5. WMatrix7 tagging output for the *Guardian* corpus (Source: Author)

While the wordclouds generated by Wmatrix7 are data rich, for current purposes, only four categories are selected for a deeper study to highlight rhetorical structures that demonstrate

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how policy-making can become politicised, and the dynamics involved in suffocating informed discussion.

The semantic tags (semtags) selected pertain to the body (given health impacts of traffic emissions), law and order¹ (given financial penalties involved), the ‘people’ (given that the *Daily Mail* claims to represent *the* people), and violence and anger (given intense, even, volatile emotions elicited). Table 6 summarises raw frequency and relative weightings per thousand words.

Table 6. Semantic tags by corpus.

Corpus	Anatomy & Physiology: B1	Law & Order: G2.1	People: S2	Violent or Angry: E3
Daily Mail	77 (1.9/1,000)	175 (4.4/1,000)	148 (3.8/1,000)	110 (2.8/1,000)
Guardian	171 (2.3/1,000)	233 (3.2/1,000)	474 (6.5/1,000)	174 (2.4/1,000)

The following section discusses some of these findings in the context of usage.

Discussion

Table 6 summarises four of multiple semantic tags attracted by each corpus. Concordance analysis is used to examine the tagged words within the context of use, with a five-word window to the left and right of the node term.

Anatomy and Physiology (B1)

A number of body parts are employed metaphorically (e.g., “the independent regulatory *arm*”, or “reluctance to *back* London’s mayor”). Many concrete uses are also found. In the *Guardian*, for example, breath (and breathing) occurs 24 times and lung/s 23 times each within the context of health, compared to only four references in the *Daily Mail* for breath(ing) and eight references for lungs. The *Guardian* appears to emphasise a public health perspective, but this seems under-represented in the *Daily Mail*.

¹Five outer London boroughs brought an anti-expansion case before the court in February 2023, which was dismissed in July.

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Anatomical and physiological references in the *Daily Mail* generally tend to be used more metaphorically than in the *Guardian*, as per the excerpts below (the key term is italicised).

- [1] going to take the criticism on the *chin*
- [2] white van men who are the red *corpuscles* in the lifeblood of the economy
- [3] Hampton Court, on the *cusp* of the stalag Ulez,
- [4] Mayor take his *fingers* out of his *ears* and listen to the misery caused by
- [5] yet another slap in the *face* from a Labour mayor.
- [6] it been forced through undemocratically in the *face* of overwhelming opposition
- [7] now he's trying to wash his *hands* of the mess
- [8] urban authorities will be looking on, licking their *lips*

The *Guardian* tends to only use physiologically-related terms metaphorically when discussing political processes, such as the following:

- [9] He wants Tories to *back* Sunak regardless
- [10] Team Sunak will *breathe* a sigh of relief and carry on
- [11] with an *eye* on Tory voters more wedded to green
- [12] the anti-Tory vote holds up in the *face* of a vigorous campaign
- [13] Ulez expansion is unfair should point the *finger* squarely at the government
- [14] he was denied a fair *hearing* by the watchdog

In citations 5 and 6, the metaphors suggest some form of violence or force being used to compel compliance, while citations 4 and 7 describe an unwillingness to listen or to take responsibility (referencing the London Mayor). There are also instances of using emotionally volatile metaphors, for example the reference in [3] to a 'stalag ULEZ', equating low emissions zones with brutal prisoner-of-war camps and in [8] implying that greed rather than public health motivates traffic emission reduction policies.

Compared with the emotional neutrality of citations 9 through 14, the quotes from the *Daily Mail* appear to favour affectively charged terms, appealing to emotion rather than reason.

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Law and Order (G2.1)

Semtag G2.1 annotates words relating to legal processes and relevant agents. Non-compliance with ULEZ results in a fine, and this is tagged 42 times, 38 of which by the *Daily Mail*, describing fines (penalties) variously as a “*stealth tax* which has raised £400 million”, as “*punitive new fines*,” or as force vectors, i.e., “penalty fines will *hit* drivers”, and so on. The trend in the *Daily Mail* implies deceit and victimisation:

[15] To *penalise* innocent people for driving to work

[16] the cost of living and then also *penalise* them, simply for driving their

[17] they just want to *penalise* drivers at every turn

[18] it in a way that doesn't *penalise* motorists.

[19] Why are we being *penalised*?

[20] Drivers are having to pay a price *penalty* to follow the rules

[21] £12.50 charge will be slapped with a *penalty* charge notice (PCN) of

[22] do without sleepless nights waiting for more *penalty* notices to arrive

In this discourse, drivers are positioned as innocent victims, going about their business but still being punished [15 through 17], while in [20], consequences for rule violations are questioned. Punishment-related terms (including ‘punitive’) occur 13 times in total, ten of which by the *Daily Mail* in describing how fines for non-compliance “punish hardworking Londoners” and the “poor first and foremost”, and that “ULEZ punishes [people] for getting on with their lives”. The emphasis in the *Daily Mail* stresses how ULEZ is unfair, punitive, unwarranted, etc., building a case obscuring benefits the policy might offer by depicting it as an infringement on people’s rights.

In this way, a sense of outrage is confected using claims that ULEZ is unfair, unjust, and that it victimises otherwise innocent people who may already be impoverished.

People (S3)

Of the 518 times ‘people’ is tagged, the *Guardian* corpus carries 418 (81%) of these references. However, given the size of the data subset, only a brief interpretation of apparent patterns are noted here.

Of the 418 *Guardian* references, 77 are from a rolling politics blog covering a by-election (July 27, 2023) which include political speeches containing themes around supporting ‘the

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people'. Other references refer to 'people' as civic entities, being provided with information, being affected by changes in legislation, dealing with the cost of living challenges, etc. The positioning of the 'people' in the *Guardian* discourse is as civic participants.

This mostly neutral tonality is not reflected in the *Daily Mail* accounts, however. In the latter, 'people' are often framed as victims, as in "penalise innocent people", "the right time to clobber people", "imposing this ULEZ tax on hard-working people", "punishing people", and so on. The framing suggests that the 'people' are under threat, while implying that the media is on their side. However, the use of 'people' is to prescribe particular roles – in this case, the people are victimised, and it is the policy in question backed by the state machinery that is weaponised as the source of such indifferent victimisation.

Violent or Angry (E3)

The last of the four tag-sets highlights how the 'war on motorists' metaphor is expressed. Anger is expressed with varying intensity, from annoyance to fury. Anger and its variations are noted 56 times, 32 times by the *Daily Mail*, with 'fury' and 'furious' occurring five times each, with variations (i.e., 'infuriated') twice, including 'wrath', 'enraged', and 'inflame'. The *Guardian* references 'anger' 10 times and 'angry' and 'outrage' four times each. The emotional tonality of the latter corpus appears to be less amplified in comparison to that of the former.

The activity or threat of violence is also tagged here. Of the violence-related words used here, the *Guardian* refers to 'abuse' some 13 times, all in relation to the widespread social media campaign against the person of the London Mayor, for his ethnicity, his politics, and his name. The *Daily Mail* for example, often published articles referring to the Mayor as "Genghis Khan," suggesting autocratic invasion and occupation. The sole use of the term 'abuse' by the *Daily Mail* concerned the Mayor's authority: "a scandalous *abuse* of the mayor's power" (August 22, 2023), which ignores the racial abuse and threats to life Khan received during this period, much of which was apparent in the headlines and article bodies published by the *Daily Mail* itself. Instead, Khan is described as the perpetrator, for "clobbering motorists" with the "sheer bone-headed cruelty" of the scheme in which drivers of non-compliant vehicles will be "forced" to "shell out".

Hit, another word connoting violence, is tagged 48 times, 29 times in the *Daily Mail*. The emphasis in this corpus is on how motorists, disabled ambulances, 'hardworking' people, and 'working families' are going to be struck forcefully by the scheme. To be fair, references to 'hit' in the *Guardian* also make this point, but this is exclusively as reported speech from quoted politicians, rather than editorial opinion.

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Conclusion

The foregoing has been a fast canter through ways that cognitive linguistics and corpus linguistic methods can help identify subtle patterns in the manner by which public opinion can become politicised due to ideology.

By reviewing the corpora of two UK politically opposing news-media around the three months covering the last stage of the ULEZ expansion through semantic tagging, it is possible to present some high-level pointers that help account for how these are effectuated in public discourse.

The *Daily Mail* was a vocal opponent of the ULEZ scheme, referring to it as a stealth tax, a punishment, penalising hard working families and disabled people and the already impoverished, and frequently turned their ire against the person of the London Mayor. The rhetorical structure of the anti-ULEZ voice, as vocalised through the *Daily Mail*, shows some clear basic patterns that require further examination.

The first among these rhetorical strategies is the use of outrage as an affective motif. By pointing out how outraged ‘the people’ are, due to the unfair treatment and suffering being imposed on them, i.e., their victimisation, the rallying call is around protection, to halt the constructed oppression. The *Daily Mail* published a number of stories about how the ULEZ enforcement cameras were being vandalised and how some groups were trying to find loopholes to not pay the enforcement fines. The newspaper vilified the London Mayor in a number of ways, contributing to a general ambience of personal persecution the Mayor endured. The newspaper also employed a range of violent and intensely angry motifs in its articles around ULEZ.

In contrast, it is actually difficult to find examples of similar rhetorical tactics in the *Guardian*. This media was, predominantly, in favour of ULEZ and made the arguments quite clearly and factually. It also reasonably identified and addressed the challenges, including how some families, already struggling, would find the ULEZ scheme challenging because they could not afford compliant vehicles for business or domestic use. Unlike the *Daily Mail* however, there are no personal pejoratives, such as ‘Genghis Khan’ to be found in the *Guardian*, unless it is a direct quotation of a Conservative politician.

The tentative conclusions drawn here then are these. The politicisation of a given policy along ideological grounds can be found in an analysis of how language is used to construct the parameters of what is termed a text-world (Gavins, 2007) or a discourse space (Chilton,

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2004). These are, in effect, mental models constructed by the audience given the information provided by the writer/ speaker.

In these discourse spaces, emotionality is favoured over reason. It is well known that emotion is processed through the limbic system of the brain triggering rapid fight-flight-freeze reactions, whereas reason is processed elsewhere and does not trigger the limbic system. Emotionality fogs reasoning. The emotional tone of the *Daily Mail* articles are further exacerbated by the repeated use of violent and angry imagery, and even tacit approval to the vandalising of ULEZ enforcement cameras. Feelings elicited require a focal point, a lightning rod, and this is achieved by creating polarised victim and persecutor roles. Politicisation evolves from the creation of these roles. The victim group are generally seen as innocent people, going about their lives, but victimised in an arbitrary manner by the existing all-powerful and unaccountable state apparatus, causing the group suffering. The source of such grievance is personified (Sadiq Khan), providing a target to be vilified, demonstrated by a significant spike in on-line personalised abuse against the London Mayor.

Once this narrative (or text-world) has been construed, it becomes a foil for public resentment, with highly charged emotional reactions. Closed to more reasoned arguments, these discourse spaces consolidate and become increasingly resistant to change. The policy becomes increasingly politicised, inevitably along ideological lines – for instance, those on the right of the Overton window support the rights of the individual over ‘society’ which Thatcher famously denounced, while those on the left support the greater good and expect some degree of compromise from individuals. The *Daily Mail* endorses the rights of individuals to resist the state’s claims of a social good, and this reinforces the ideological framing of public policy in a manner that can be readily re-invoked by pitching it as a binary battle between ‘society’ versus the ‘individual’.

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